

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE (ES)

OCCUR <https://ecoinformatic.shinyapps.io/OCCUR/> es una aplicación que guía paso a paso el proceso de selección de filtros para la limpieza y validación de registros de especies disponibles. Este flujo de trabajo interactivo ayudará al usuario en la selección de datos entre múltiples opciones disponibles según su caso de estudio.

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the OCCUR logo and a menu of modules: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, References, and About. The main content area has a purple header with 'OCCUR app' and a 'SOURCE' link. Below the header is an information icon and a paragraph describing the app's purpose. A central 'INSTRUCTIONS' section lists 8 steps, with a flow diagram showing the sequence: Basis Of Record (blue) → Taxonomy (orange) → Geography (purple) → Time (green) → Duplicates (dark blue). To the right is a 'Trade-off' diagram with 'DATA COVERAGE' on the y-axis and 'FILTER STRICTNESS' on the x-axis. A solid diagonal line shows that as filter strictness increases, data coverage decreases. A dotted diagonal line shows that as filter strictness increases, data certainty increases. Three funnel icons are placed at different points along these lines, and a blue wedge below the x-axis indicates the range of filter strictness. Below the diagram is a caption: 'Variation in the number of records available data coverage (continuous line) and data certainty estimates (dotted line) based on precision and accuracy of records information'.

OCCUR app SOURCE

i OCCUR app is a "step by step" guide that goes over 5 different modules to curate biodiversity data records. It was created to facilitate the process of filtering, cleaning and validating occurrence species records from data repositories. This interactive workflow will help the user in the selection of data records between all possibilities depending on their study case, considering their pros and cons. Each module will also display how data certainty and data coverage change when selecting different scenarios of the application of filtering and cleaning rules.

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Choose a module of the 5 available in the left panel.
2. Select between filters / steps in left-upper box (there are no previous selections marked).
3. Check the "Trade-off" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (left panel).
4. Check the "Methods" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (middle panel).
5. Check and copy the "R Code" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (right panel).
6. See the bibliography associated in the "References" panel.
7. Check how certainty and data coverage varies with each selection in the left-bottom panel to make your final selection. Values goes from 0 (minimum certainty or data coverage available) to 1 (maximum certainty or data coverage available).
8. Download the final guide to process data and write the methods section based on the selected steps by module in the "Final report" tab.

DATA COVERAGE **DATA CERTAINTY**

FILTER STRICTNESS

Variation in the number of records available data coverage (continuous line) and data certainty estimates (dotted line) based on precision and accuracy of records information

OCCUR presenta 5 módulos diferentes según la dimensión a tratar en los datos de biodiversidad.

1. Elige un módulo entre los 5 disponibles en el panel izquierdo.

OCCUR app SOURCE

OCCUR

- Basis of Record
- Taxonomic
- Geographic
- Temporal
- Duplicates
- Final Report
- References
- About

i OCCUR app is a "step by step" guide that goes over 5 different modules to curate biodiversity data records. It was created to facilitate the process of filtering, cleaning and validating occurrence species records from data repositories. This interactive workflow will help the user in the selection of data records between all possibilities depending on their study case, considering their pros and cons. Each module will also display how data certainty and data coverage change when selecting different scenarios of the application of filtering and cleaning rules.

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Choose a module of the 5 available in the left panel.
2. Select between filters / steps in left-upper box (there are no previous selections marked).
3. Check the "Trade-off" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (left panel).
4. Check the "Methods" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (middle panel).
5. Check and copy the "R Code" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (right panel).
6. See the bibliography associated in the "References" panel.
7. Check how certainty and data coverage varies with each selection in the left-bottom panel to make your final selection. Values goes from 0 (minimum certainty or data coverage available) to 1 (maximum certainty or data coverage available).
8. Download the final guide to process data and write the methods section based on the selected steps by module in the "Final report" tab.

Flowchart: Basis Of Record → Taxonomy → Geography → Time → Duplicates

Trade-off Diagram: A graph with **DATA COVERAGE** on the y-axis and **DATA CERTAINTY** on the x-axis. A solid line slopes downwards from top-left to bottom-right, and a dotted line slopes upwards from bottom-left to top-right. Three funnel icons are placed at different points along these lines. Below the graph is a **FILTER STRICTNESS** scale with three circular gauges.

Variation in the number of records available data coverage (continuous line) and data certainty estimates (dotted line) based on precision and accuracy of records information

2. Selecciona entre los filtros / pasos disponibles en el panel superior-izquierdo (ninguna opción está seleccionada previamente).

OCCUR app SOURCE

In order to validate records geographically, the user may choose what type of data needs before download (this step can also be taken after the download process by filtering the dataset)

Choose between:

- Do not apply previous filters
- Only records with coordinates
- Only records with coordinates filtered by spatial extent (area or administrative units)
- Only records without known coordinate issues

Trade-off Methods R Code

Pros	Cons
Depending on the selected area, can exclude unreliable records (e.g. zero coordinates, sea points, etc.)	Excludes records from suitable/native regions not considered by bibliography.
Excludes records from introduced distributional areas.	Excludes georeferenciable records by locality information that could be repaired.
Less time of manipulation than download all available records with coordinates.	
More information available including records labelled as 'with coordinates issues'.	

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value:
- *Recovering coordinates:
- *Detecting environmental outliers:
- *Checking coordinates precision:
- *Checking coordinates position:
- *Detecting distributional outliers:

Bar Chart:

Category	Value (min to max)
Certainty	High
Data coverage	Medium

3. Valida la información disponible con cada selección en la tabla "Trade-off" en la primera pestaña del panel superior-derecho.

OCCUR app

OCCUR

- Basis of Record
- Taxonomic
- 1. Download records options
- 2. Choose type of taxonomical source for standardize / harmonize
- 3. Filters based on taxonomical information included
- 4. Query species names with taxonomical database
- Geographic
- Temporal
- Duplicates
- Final Report
- References
- About

In order to validate records geographically, the user may choose what type of data needs before download (this step can also be taken after the download process by filtering the dataset)

Choose between:

- Do not apply previous filters
- Only records with coordinates
- Only records with coordinates filtered by spatial extent (area or administrative units)
- Only records without known coordinate issues

Category	Value (min to max)
Certainty	High
Data coverage	Medium

SOURCE

Trade-off | Methods | R Code

Pros	Cons
Depending on the selected area, can exclude unreliable records (e.g. zero coordinates, sea points, etc.)	Excludes records from suitable/native regions not considered by bibliography.
Excludes records from introduced distributional areas.	Excludes georeferencible records by locality information that could be repaired.
Less time of manipulation than download all available records with coordinates.	
More information available including records labelled as 'with coordinates issues'.	

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value:
- *Recovering coordinates:
- *Detecting environmental outliers:
- *Checking coordinates precision:
- *Checking coordinates position:
- *Detecting distributional outliers:

5. Revisa la bibliografía asociada en el panel "References". Para acceder al documento original haz click en 'See ref' y se abrirá el enlace en tu buscador.

The image shows two screenshots of the OCCUR app interface. The top screenshot displays the 'References' panel, which lists various scientific papers related to data cleaning and distribution analysis. The bottom screenshot shows the 'SOURCE' panel, which provides details about the 'CoordinateCleaner' R package, including its version (2.0-20) and a list of references. A dashed yellow box highlights the 'CoordinateCleaner::cc_outl [17]' entry in the 'SOURCE' panel, indicating the specific reference being discussed in the text.

OCCUR app

Use distributional information | Use environmental information

Choose between:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers.

OCCUR app | **SOURCE**

Trade-off | Methods | R code

Use distributional information | Use environmental information

Point in polygon function using range maps shapefiles.

CoordinateCleaner::cc_junc

CoordinateCleaner::cc_outl [17]

Bracatus' R package [23]

OCCUR app | **SOURCE**

Home

Basis of Record

Taxonomic

Geographic

1. Previous filters in download process

2. Location check

3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations

4. Outliers check

Temporal

Duplicates

Final Report

References

About

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[3] Shirey, V., Belitz, M.W., Barve, V. and Guralnick, R. (2021), A complete inventory of North American butterfly occurrence data: narrowing data gaps, but increasing bias. *Ecography*, 44: 537-547 See ref

[4] Tiago, X., Ceia-Hasse, A., Marques, T.A. et al. (2017). Spatial distribution of citizen science casuistic observations for different taxonomic groups. *Sci Rep* 7, 12832 See ref

[5] Feng, X., Park, D.S., Walker, C. et al. (2019). A checklist for maximizing reproducibility of ecological niche models. *Nat Ecol Evol* 3, 1382-1395 See ref

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precision:
position:
outliers: TRUE

6. Muchas opciones disponibles en OCCUR muestran un ejemplo simple de código R disponible para copiar en el portapapeles e integrar en los scripts de los usuarios. La tabla está disponible en la tercera pestaña del panel superior-derecho.

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the OCCUR logo and navigation options: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, 1. Previous filters in download process, 2. Location check, 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations, 4. Outliers check, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, References, and About.

The main panel has two tabs: "Use distributional information" and "Use environmental information". Under "Choose between:", there are four radio button options:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers

 Below the options is a bar chart with a vertical axis from "min" to "max". The x-axis has two categories: "Certainty" and "Data coverage". The "Certainty" bar is significantly taller than the "Data coverage" bar.

The right-hand panel, titled "SOURCE", has three tabs: "Trade-off", "Methods", and "R code". The "R code" tab is active and contains the following code:


```
library(sf) # Point in polygon analysis
# Upload dataframe with occurrences (occData) and shapefile of administrative units (countriesSHP)

datapoints <- st_as_sf(x = occData, coords = c('decimalLongitude', 'decimalLatitude'), crs = '+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs')

occData <- st_join(datapoints, countriesSHP)
```

 A "Copy" button is located above the code. Below the code, a "Your selection:" summary shows:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value: *
- *Recovering coordinates: *
- *Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates precision: *
- *Checking coordinates position: *
- *Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE

 A location pin icon is visible in the bottom right corner of this panel.

7. Valida como varía la certidumbre y disponibilidad de los datos con cada selección en el panel inferior-izquierdo. Los valores mostrados van desde el mínimo al máximo disponible según la bibliografía indicada.

OCCUR app
☰
SOURCE

- 👁 Basis of Record
- 🏠 Taxonomic <
- 📍 Geographic <
- 1. Previous filters in download process
- 2. Location check
- 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations
- 4. Outliers check
- 🕒 Temporal
- 📄 Duplicates
- 📄 Final Report
- 📄 References
- 📄 About

Use distributional information
Use environmental information

Choose between:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers

Category	Level
Certainty	max
Data coverage	~75%

Trade-off
Methods
R code

Copy

```

library(sf) # Point in polygon analysis

# Upload dataframe with occurrences (occData) and shapefile of administrative units (countriesSHP)

datapoints <- st_as_sf(x = occData, coords = c('decimalLongitude', 'decimalLatitude'), crs = '+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs')

occData <- st_join(datapoints, countriesSHP)
                    
```

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value: TRUE
- *Recovering coordinates: TRUE
- *Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates precision: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates position: TRUE
- *Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE

8. Valida las opciones marcadas en cada módulo mirando el panel inferior-derecho.

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, and a list of steps (1-4) including '4. Outliers check'. The main area has two tabs: 'Use distributional information' and 'Use environmental information'. Under 'Choose between:', option 'b' is selected. Below this is a bar chart with 'Certainty' and 'Data coverage' on the x-axis and 'min' to 'max' on the y-axis. The 'Certainty' bar is significantly higher than the 'Data coverage' bar. On the right, there are tabs for 'Trade-off', 'Methods', and 'R code', with the 'R code' tab active, showing a code block. At the bottom right, a pink summary box is highlighted with a yellow border, containing the text 'Your selection:' followed by a list of selected options and a location pin icon.

OCCUR app

Use distributional information Use environmental information

Choose between:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers

max

min

Certainty Data coverage

Trade-off Methods R code

Copy

```
library(sf) # Point in polygon analysis

# Upload dataframe with occurrences (occData) and shapefile of administrative units (countriesSHP)

datapoints <- st_as_sf(x = occData, coords = c('decimalLongitude', 'decimalLatitude'), crs = '+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs')

occData <- st_join(datapoints, countriesSHP)
```

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value: TRUE
- *Recovering coordinates: TRUE
- *Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates precision: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates position: TRUE
- *Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE

9. Pulsa el botón 'Download' disponible en el panel 'Final report' para descargar un archivo txt con tu guía final. Incluye los pasos seleccionados para procesar los datos y escribir tu sección de métodos en base a la información de cada módulo.

OCCUR app SOURCE

OCCUR

Basis of Record

Taxonomic

Geographic

>> 1. Previous filters in download process

>> 2. Location check

>> 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations

>> 4. Outliers check

Temporal

Duplicates

Final Report

References

About

----- FINAL REPORT -----

Based on the steps selected in OCCUR App, the summary of methods chose by the user to filter and clean biodiversity records is:

Basis of Record: The user will filter records to select Observations

*Taxonomical check sums up following the steps:

1. Download option NOT PROVIDED
2. The taxonomical source for standardization / harmonization will be:
Type AUTOMATIC;
Spatial coverage GLOBAL;
Taxonomical coverage GENERAL;
using Matching Type EXACT
3. Selecting only records identified at a proper taxonomic rank
4. Selecting records with or without authorship information in their scientific name
5. Including scientific names classified with taxonomical status: Accepted

*Geographical check sums up the following the steps:

1. Previous filters in download process: Only records without known coordinate issues
2. Location check:
 - Check coordinates precision: Use number of decimal digits of coordinates as a measure of their precision
 - Validate records based on whether coordinates values are out of a reliable range
 - Validate coordinates position
3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations: Do not correct coordinate values
4. Distributional Outliers check: Do not apply
5. Environmental Outliers check: Do not apply

*Temporal information filter as: Data with no temporal range using Date of collection

Finally the identification and deletion of *duplicate records* will be done as the combination of same species Cell Year Recorder

The user agrees to use this final report as a guide to process their data and rewrite this text to avoid conflicts due to plagiarism.

Download